

WAYS OF INTRODUCING INNOVATION INTO THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

Ochilova Nigora Ruzimuratovna

*Associate Professor of General Methodology Department, University of
Economics and Pedagogy*

Abstract: in our country, the development of new models of educational services has become a priority in order to increase its efficiency by introducing innovation into the educational system, to open the way to its individualization and effective use of educational services. In this regard, extensive work is being done in our country.

Key words: information resources, information and communication technologies in general education schools, optical fiber communication lines, schools connected to the Internet.

At the heart of the reforms in all spheres currently being carried out in Uzbekistan are the establishment of a humane, democratic, legal state and society, as well as the promotion to higher levels of socio-economic and cultural development, serving the realization of the noble goals aimed at taking a worthy place in the ranks of the world community. The achievement of these goals depends, first of all, on the effective organization of educational activities aimed at teaching the young generation the basics of scientific knowledge, creating a broad worldview and scope of thinking, and forming their spiritual and moral qualities.

The goal is to inform all stages of education and further improve the provision of interactive services to the population. As a result, the educational process is improved and wide opportunities are created to improve the quality of the educational process. Here, let's focus on the following statistics.

ZiyONET information and education portal: Number of connected schools - 9427.

Educational videos - 23,000.

Created satellite sites - 5600.

Today, it is impossible to talk about the modernization and renewal of our country, achieving sustainable development, without the wide development of information and communication technologies and the Internet system. It should be said that there are a number of problems in the field, including the insufficient functioning of mobile communication and the Internet network, which reduce its quality level, insufficient attention is paid to the issues of implementation of projects for the introduction of modern information technologies and communications, the current system of training, retraining and professional development of personnel in the field of information technologies and communications does not take into account the rapid pace of development of IT technologies, as well as the need of foreign countries to introduce advanced methods of education the fact that it does not allow to organize effective communication with leading educational institutions is an obstacle to the rapid development of the field.

This decree, adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, focuses on further improvement of the management system in the field of information technologies and communications, expansion of the spectrum of electronic state services and telecommunications services, development of telecommunications infrastructure, and specific tasks are defined in the decree.

In particular, it is indicated that, based on the best practices of leading foreign companies and educational institutions, it is necessary to organize strategic and project management, management, marketing scientific research and development, personnel training, retraining and professional development in the field of information technologies and communications.

One of the priority tasks in the modernization of education is the development of personnel potential and informatization 271, and the formation of information and communication competence for pedagogues and all participants of the educational process. The introduction of a new model of education based on the use of ICT imposes new requirements on pedagogues and all participants of the educational process, who:

- to collect, process, transfer, and store information resources, and to perform informational activity on the information product in order to automate the process of information-methodical supply;

- organization of informational interdependence between the participants of the educational process and interactive tools implemented on the basis of ICT tools;

- application and creation of psychological-pedagogical methods that diagnose and test the student's level of knowledge and assessment methodology;

- implementation of educational activities with the use of ICT tools that show the important aspects of a specific educational subject;

Given the systematic and comprehensive approach proposed by UNESCO, the above requirements do not specify the specific technologies and services that a teacher should have (or should not). Undoubtedly, the content of ICT education should be determined by understanding the state of modern information technologies available in the educational process and their development prospects.

At the same time, in order to bring the requirements of the teacher's professional standard to the level of the special technologies needed by the teacher, it is necessary to take into account the current trends in the improvement of educational information technologies in the world educational practice, and not the current situation of local general education schools.

Management includes information exchange and referral methods, support tools, and key processes in e-learning. The moral and ethical direction reflects the ethical and legal norms related to the use of personal information about the learner. The technological direction includes the planning of infrastructure, standard, technical and software of e-learning environment. Based on the above, the following can be recommended to educational institutions:

- further development of wide introduction of ICT in the educational process;

- formation of ICT competence among professors and teachers;

- regularly get acquainted with foreign experience in teaching subjects and take measures to introduce them to educational institutions in a timely manner;

- development of new interactive pedagogical methods and methods for improving the quality of education;
- installation of video surveillance devices in auditoriums in order to improve the efficiency of using modern ICT tools to control the quality of lessons during the educational process. In this, the tasks to be carried out in the future are determined by observing the classes of professors and teachers;
- creating conditions for students to learn independently.

Therefore, the rapid development of the globalization process throughout the world, the increasing demand for competitive personnel, including the study of the requirements for personnel, as well as the issues of organizing a high-quality and acceptable educational process for all, are paid special attention in the "Education-2030" concept program adopted by UNESCO.

In short, as a response to the demand that arose in society, the problem of artificial intelligence in general education schools, methods of expressing knowledge using information technologies and managing them appeared. All this is aimed at improving the quality of education. The rapid development of information technologies forces the educational system to take a step forward. The possibilities of information technology tools have created opportunities to clearly see several interdisciplinary relationships.

List of references:

1. Azizkhujayev N.N. Modern pedagogical technologies (Advertising - plans). - Tashkent, 2002.
2. Askarov M, Hayitboev M, Nishonov M, Pedagogy. Textbook.-T.: Interpretation 2008.-289 pages.
3. Ochilov M. New pedagogical technologies. - Karshi "Nasaf", 2000
4. Elboeva Shakhnoza Buriniyozovna. Legal basis of activity of national culture center in Uzbekistan. science and innovation international scientific journal volume 1 issue 8 uif-2022: 8.2 | issn: 2181-3337.p.358-362.

5. Kurbanova Marguba Boltaevna. Creation of the national corpus of the uzbek language in the implementation of the language policy. ISSN: 2776-0979, Volume 3, Issue 11, Nov., 2022